

Protocol: Magnesium Aggregate Synthesis at Stanford University

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Magnesium aggregates are synthesized via a high-temperature evaporation–condensation process using a modified vertical tube furnace (SPG, Catalytic Instruments GmbH & Co. KG). The furnace system is designed to generate high number concentrations of thermally stable solid particles in a controlled and repeatable manner, ensuring strong day-to-day reproducibility. Within the furnace, narrowly distributed magnesium nanoparticles are continuously produced by heating the lower section of a high-purity alumina tube (99.7% purity; outer diameter 15 mm, inner diameter 11 mm, length 170 mm; Almath Crucibles Ltd), which contains solid magnesium chips (6–35 mesh, ≥99.98% purity; Sigma-Aldrich). Owing to the comparatively high vapor pressure of magnesium at elevated temperatures, significant evaporation occurs at temperatures above approximately 550 °C. To prevent oxidation and unwanted reactions, the system is operated under a reducing atmosphere consisting of high-purity argon with 3% hydrogen (specialty gas; Linde). The generated magnesium vapor is transported downstream through a secondary alumina tube (outer diameter 10 mm, inner diameter 7 mm, length 255 mm) by the carrier gas flow (2 SLPM). As the vapor exits the high-temperature zone and enters a region of decreasing temperature, rapid cooling induces supersaturation, leading to homogeneous nucleation. In this stage, magnesium atoms collide and coalesce to form primary nanoparticles (Figure 1, left). Further downstream, these primary particles undergo agglomeration primarily via diffusion-limited aggregation, forming larger fractal-like magnesium aggregates. A residence chamber is incorporated to promote the formation of larger “super-aggregates.” Additional dilution with high-purity nitrogen (grade 5.0; Linde) is introduced (2 - 10 SLPM) in this region to control particle concentration, residence time, and collision frequency, thereby enabling control over aggregate growth dynamics, morphology, and final size distribution. A schematic of the experimental setup is shown in Figure 1 (center). The furnace temperature is regulated using a silicon carbide (SiC) resistance heater (IPS Ceramics), coupled with an S-type thermocouple and a PID control loop, allowing precise and stable thermal control. Magnesium feedstock loading is performed in an argon-filled glovebox to minimize exposure to oxygen and moisture. The system inlet and outlet are carefully sealed during transfer and between furnace operations to maintain an inert environment. Aggregates are collected downstream using in-line filtration onto lacey carbon-supported copper grids (300 mesh; Sigma-Aldrich). The collected samples are subsequently characterized using a FEI Tecnai G2 F20 X-TWIN transmission electron microscope (TEM), as shown in Figure 1 (right).

Figure 1: Synthesis principle (left, C. Jourdain PhD thesis), modified furnace (center), and TEM example of Mg aggregates (right).